

EVALUATION OF EVIDENCE USED: NATIONAL WASTE POLICY 2018

Presented By
Chi-Hsuan Wu

MONASH
University

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Student: Chi-Hsuan Wu

Student Number: 35606819

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1. Introduction

The global environmental issue is becoming serious, making waste management a key sustainability topic. In Australia, the waste is growing faster than economic growth, which has a huge impact for environment and threaten public health. To response, the Australian government launched the “National Waste Policy” in 2018. The core concept of the policy is to promote circular economy, through highly efficient of recycling and waste reduction strategies to minimize environmental impact (Ghosh, 2020).

The ‘National Waste Policy’ stipulates five key principles, which include avoiding waste, improving resource recovery, increasing use of recycled materials, better managing material flows, and improving information to support innovation. However, the policy faces challenges in transparency and quality, as many actions and plans lack explicit supporting data or citations, which creates uncertainty in its future implementation and evaluation.

Part A of this white paper will evaluate how well the policy communicates these ideas and uses evidence to support its goals. It will assess the use of evidence in the ‘National Waste Policy’ and suggest improvement. By analysing the quality and transparency of this policy, this paper will explore ways to strengthen the evidence base for the policy in circular economy practice and propose short-term and long-term improvement strategies.

2. Assessment

2.1 Overview of evidence use in the policy

The 2018 National Waste Policy was built based on the National Waste Policy 2009. There are some differences between these two versions such as the 2009 policy

focusing on reducing waste, while the 2018 policy concentrates on avoiding waste, which improves the response to changes in the international waste market and helps Australia switch to a more circular economy (Flowers, 2021). Most of the introduction and purpose section use evidences by third parties and organizations who produce reports for government like The Centre For International Economics or Access Economics, and the audience can easily access the official resources. However, their credibility can be questioned, Access Economics (2009) states that “While every effort has been made to ensure the accuracy of this document, the uncertain nature of economic data forecasting and analysis means that Access Economics Pty Limited is unable to make any warranties in relation to the information contained herein.”

The policy emphasizes the value of circular economic, but its transparency and use of evidence are unclear. For instance, the policy mentions increasing the waste recycling rate and promoting product stewardship, but does not illustrate what research data or empirical research results have been used in implementations. This might be because the complexity of waste management data collection, which involves a wide range of interested parties like investors, corporations, and politics, making it difficult for policymakers to integrate comprehensive evidence to support the policy.

2.2 Strengthening the volume of evidence in the policy

Based on the assessment in 2.1 above, there are two key areas need to improve, which can reinforce the credibility of the policy.

2.2.1 Waste management rate

The policy mentions increasing the waste recycling rate, which is a major goal of promoting a circular economy. However, the lack of specific

data to support effect evaluation like recycling rate, the methods for archiving recycle goals, and the results of recycling measurements, causes readers to mistrust the quality of the evidence (Oliver et al., 2014). Thus, the policy should add more data using a qualitative method in the evaluation stage, including recycling data from every area, the recycling rate for different types of waste, and long-term recycling effectiveness measurements. These would become reliable resources for future adjustment.

2.2.2 The strategy of circular economy

The government built the circular economy principles based on The European Commission Circular Economy Action Plan in 2015, and adopted them to suit Australia. However, there is no evidence or data in their strategy to support their ideas and plans, which makes readers question the feasibility of the plan. Therefore, it should provide more data and evidence, for instance, recycling data from local business, data on resource usage, or successful cases from other countries, to strengthen the credibility of the policy. This data and evidence need to be included in the design and implementation stages.

2.3 Improving evidence quality and transparency in policy

Although the policy provides some evidence, there are two significant areas where quality and transparency still need improvement to ensure trust and effectiveness.

2.3.1 The data and information in graphs

The policy includes various graphs to provide the audience with a clear and logical vision of the data and their connections, such as the data on

Australian waste generation or Australian waste flow relationship diagram. Nevertheless, the graphs lack clear sourcing. As a result, readers cannot access the original sources to get more information and nor can they determine the reliability of the data. Hence, the data should be reviewed by peers who are specialists or scholars in relevant areas, so that readers can have confidence in the accuracy and credibility of the information presented in the policy.

2.3.2 The circular economy principles

As mentioned in 2.2.2., the strategy of the circular economy needs more evidence to support its implementation and the achievement of its goals. Therefore, the quality of evidence must meet higher standards with valid peer-reviewed data and sources. It should also combine multiple lines of evidence to reduce bias and help decision-making. Moreover, making this data open to the public would allow for monitoring of the government's actions and progress.

3. Strategies

This section outlines the short-term and long-term strategies based on ASP2000 suggestions for improvement areas in 2.2 and 2.3. The strategies are summarized in Table 1 below for clarity.

3.1 Optimizing waste management rate

Some adjustments are needed in the formulation stage as short-term strategy for improving the waste management rate. In the policymaking process, the government should use available valid data sources, for example recycling data from local governments or businesses, to help in initial assessments and measurements.

Although, it is very complex and difficult to apply in practice (Bullock et al., 2021), it can provide immediate data support before policy implementation. Specifically, the initial assessment should use recycling data from different regions and types of waste and integrate this data into the policymaking process to ensure accomplishment of recycle targets.

The Evaluation stage of waste management needs a data collection and monitoring system, especially for the recycling rate. The government must set a national standard for data collection, including recycling data from every region, different types of waste, and key performance indicators for recycling. This is not only tracking the long-term performance and assessment of recycling but also helps policymakers adjust future policies more effectively based on practice conditions.

3.2 Enhancing circular economy strategy

To improve the consultation stage of the circular economy, it is essential to rapidly capture data on the circular economy and use it to support policy, which needs to cooperate with local firms and other interest parties. By using successful circular economy cases from local businesses or other countries, such as fruit industry (Campos et al., 2020) or mining industry (Köpman et al., 2023), the effectiveness of the strategy can be demonstrated, so increasing public and stakeholder support. Moreover, workshops and expert consultations provide actual data, which can enhance the credibility and feasibility of the policy.

Adjustments in the anticipation stage can help the circular economy develop a long-term strategy. The government should systematically collect data from local businesses and resource usage, while referring to successful experiences from other countries and absorb them into policy design.

Furthermore, the communication between experts and policymakers can create a continuous mechanism for updating and sharing data (Likens, 2010; Choi et al., 2005). Thus, these methods can ensure feasibility, credibility, and scientific rigor in the design stage.

3.3 Improving data and graphical representation

The adoption stage should supplement every graph with data sources to secure that all data has clear source annotations and can be queried and verified within the policy. This can increase transparency and give readers confidence in the accuracy and reliability of the policy (Bennett, 2016).

For long-term strategy, the evaluation stage must establish a mechanism for peer review and data transparency to ensure the data in the graphs can be reviewed by experts and the public. This not only raises the credibility of the data but also allows public to monitor the progress of the policy.

3.4 Strengthening evidence for circular economy principles

The formulation stage should use available circular economy data and successful cases from other countries to provide immediate data support for the policy. The data needs to fit local circumstances to ensure relevance and adaptable of the policy and rise credibility.

The policy should build a multiple line of evidence system in the anticipation stage as long-term strategy, where data from scholars, local businesses, and international cases undergoes peer review. For example, the smart waste management technology that uses the Digital Urban Waste Tracking System in Poland (Strzelecka, 2024). At the start of policy design stage, evidence should be included to guarantee the quality and transparency of the strategy. Again, the data and evidence should be published for public monitoring to ensures the effectiveness and feasibility of the policy.

Table 1: Improvement areas of the policy cycle

Improvement area	Short-term strategy (ASP2000)	Details	Long-term strategy (ASP2000)	Details
Waste management rate	Formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use available data for initial assessment. ● Integrate data into policymaking to meet recycling targets. 	Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establish a data collection and monitoring system. ● Set national standards and track long-term performance.
The strategy of circular economy	Consultation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Capture data quickly and collaborate with local firms and stakeholders. ● Use successful circular economy cases from local businesses and other countries to demonstrate strategy effectiveness and gain support. ● Hold workshops and expert consultations to enhance credibility. 	Anticipation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Systematically collect data from local businesses and resource usage. ● Integrate successful international experiences into policy design. ● Foster communication between experts and policymakers to create a continuous data-sharing mechanism.
The data and information in graphs	Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ensure every graph includes clear data source annotations for transparency and verifiability. 	Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Establish a peer review and data transparency mechanism. ● Allow experts and public to review data, increasing credibility and enabling progress monitoring.
The circular economy principles	Formulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use available circular economy data and successful international cases for immediate data support. ● Ensure data relevance to local circumstances to 	Anticipation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Build a multi-evidence system, involving peer-reviewed data from scholars, businesses and international cases. ● Include evidence in the policy design stage to

		enhance policy credibility.		guarantee quality and transparency. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Publish data for public monitoring to ensure policy effectiveness and feasibility.
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Source: Author

4. Conclusion

This paper has analysed the quality and transparency of the ‘National Waste Policy’, it promotes Australia’s circular economy but is limited by insufficient transparency and evidence. Strengthening data collection, incorporating peer-reviewed research, and implementing public monitoring will enhance the policy’s credibility and feasibility. This can ensure better decision-making and supporting a successful transition to a sustainable waste management system.

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